

Weekly Progress Report

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Plans:

- To move the Bergen Prototype to the outside weather station
- To discuss suggested changes to Bergen Prototype
- To discuss WIMEA and PhD progress

Activities:

- Initial test of connectivity between Weather Station at Florida and tower on the GFI building was done with positive results.
- All sensor nodes were moved into the Florida weather station and connectivity tests done. Checking signal strength of the nodes given their orientation and restoring 10m node report mask
- Conclusive discussion on alternative gateway excluding Raspberry Pi. Proposed to use Contiki powered sink node connected straight onto 2G/3G module
- Introductory session on getting started with programming contiki operating system
- Brainstormed ideas on what to do while in Bergen and Produce reports for as detailed in the next section
- Presented PhD work plans
- Firmware updating on all nodes
- Discussions on collaboration tools for the project members
- Discussion and viewing of the pagoda radiation shields

Suggested Areas for investigation

- Effect of weather on signal strength and link quality
- Pagoda weather shield testing, particularly in African where there is enough sunshine
- Bergen prototype Version 1 Automatic weather station
- Contiki
- Solar panel design
- Ultra Capacitors in terms of charging and discharging
- Solar energy
- Security aspects in relation to ISO 27000 security standard